

Improving handgun detection through a combination of visual features and body pose-based data

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ABSTRACT

Early detection of the presence of dangerous objects such as handguns in Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) images is vital to reduce the potential damage. In this work, a novel method for automatic detection of handguns in CCTV-like images based on a combination architecture which leverages body pose estimation is proposed. Weapon appearance features along with body pose features are combined to perform robust detection in typical surveillance environments where appearance features alone are not sufficient (e.g., because the handgun may appear too small or dark). Both CNN and recent transformer-based architectures are applied for visual feature extraction. Experiments on multiple datasets show that this approach improves state-of-the-art pose-based handgun detectors. An ablation study is also performed to verify the contribution of the pose processing branch and the false positive filter.

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, the vast majority of public and private buildings have a network of security cameras or CCTV surveillance systems. These systems allow the supervision of these spaces and the detection of threats or security risks. It is demonstrated that rapid identification and response to this type of threats significantly reduces the damage caused [1].

Currently, most systems require human operators to monitor these images. In addition, each operator must control the video sequences of multiple security cameras simultaneously. This fact, along with inherent human characteristics such as fatigue or loss of attention over time, can lead to ignoring important events or responding too late, causing significant damage and making these video surveillance systems inefficient or useless [2,3].

Unfortunately, dangerous events involving firearms are becoming more common. Some examples of these events are mass shootings, handgun attacks, gunfire incidents on school grounds or terrorist attacks [4,5]. Many of these situations could be avoided or greatly mitigated through early detection of dangerous objects or suspicious behaviours in live CCTV video.

The inclusion of intelligent systems that automatically recognize dangerous objects or behaviours can significantly help operators to respond to these threats. In recent years, machine learning systems are experiencing significant progress, particularly within the computer vision field. Recent deep learning-based architectures have achieved impressive results in tasks such as image recognition, object detection, image segmentation or data generation, mainly thanks to the appearance of CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks).

However, deep architectures are still not perfect and have some significant drawbacks, especially when there are variations between the data used during model training and the data captured at run time in the end-user scenario. For object detection models, this often leads to particularly undesirable situations, such as missing objects of interest i.e. FN (False Negative), or the incorrect detection of them, i.e. FP (False Positive). An automatic weapon detection system that generates a large number of FPs would cause the system to be disconnected. Another important consideration is that most of these architectures are based solely on the appearance of the object of interest. Nevertheless, for some tasks, such as the one discussed in this article, including more contextual information may help to reduce FNs and FPs.

The main contributions of this work are: (1) the development of a new weapon detection architecture, specifically for handguns, based on adding body pose information, which helps to improve overall detection performance, (2) a simple and light architecture

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to process the body pose data, (3) a data augmentation method based on a 3D monocular pose detector to generate a large number of pose variations and (4) the use of recent transformer-based architectures for visual feature extraction.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the existing work on handgun detection, including both classic and recent approaches. Section 3 explains the proposed method. The experiments carried out and the results obtained are summarized in Section 4 and analyzed in Section 5. Finally, conclusions and future work are presented in Section 6.

2. Related work

The first approaches to automatic weapon detection were focused on recognizing them in X-ray images using classical machine learning methods. In 2013, Flitton *et al.* [6] made a comparison of various 3D feature descriptors applied to the problem of object detection in 3D CT imagery. Classic machine learning methods have also been applied for handgun recognition in standard RGB images for video surveillance purposes. Tiwari and Verma [7] proposed an automatic handgun detection pipeline based on a combination of Harris interest point detectors and Fast Retina Keypoint (FREAK) descriptors to locate the handgun.

In parallel with the great performance obtained by CNN-based classifiers, multiple deep learning architectures have been proposed for firearms detection. First approaches were based on sliding windows, in which thousands of regions are extracted from the original image and passed through a CNN to classify each of them [8]. The main drawback of this family of methods is the large amount of computations needed to process all of these regions, which makes it difficult to apply in real time systems.

Other approaches are based on selecting only a few candidate regions (i.e., region proposals) in the image. Then, object classification and bounding box refinement is performed for each region. This family of detectors are also known as two-stage detectors. The region-based CNN (R-CNN) [9] was the first architecture under this approach and its last iteration, Faster-RCNN [10], includes several improvements in terms of speed and performance (e.g., a Region Proposal Network). In 2018, Olmos *et al.* [11] compared sliding window and region proposals methods for handgun detection. The best results were obtained by Faster R-CNN, with a VGG16 CNN as backbone for feature extraction, trained on their own dataset. On the other hand, one-stage detectors such as YOLO [12], RetinaNet [13] or SSD [14] perform object classification and bounding box regression directly without using pre-generated candidate region proposals. These architectures usually have faster inference times, which makes them more suitable for mobile devices. Several works have recently used YOLOv3 for handgun detection [15,16], which are basically direct implementations of YOLOv3 trained on custom handgun datasets. Moreover, Salazar Gonzalez *et al.* [17] proposed a method that improves Faster-RCNN performance for handgun detection applying a two stage training procedure, based on both synthetic and real images.

All the above works are solely based on the visual appearance of the object of interest and no additional context information was taken into account, making these methods prone to generating more FPs and FNs, specially in difficult cases. Some recent works, however, are showing how the inclusion of body pose information can be beneficial for weapon recognition, especially handguns. In 2019, Abruzzo *et al.* [18] proposed a method for assessing the threat level based on body posture. First, a YOLO detector is applied for locating people and handguns. Then, a pose detector is used for retrieving the body keypoint coordinates and, finally, a feed-forward network is trained to classify the threat level into three different classes based on the pose estimation. Basit

et al. [19] also proposed an architecture for identifying human-handgun pairs (i.e., firearm carriers) based on the relative position between located humans and handguns. First, handguns and humans are detected separately. Each detected human is then paired with each detected handgun, creating a paired bounding box that contains both object and the human. Finally, a CNN is trained to classify these paired bounding boxes into human carrying the identified firearm or not. In this way, this method can be used as a handgun detector taking as the detection output those handguns that are classified as a positive human-handgun pair (i.e., a human is carrying that handgun). The major drawback of both approaches is that they depend on the base detector performance (such as YOLO or Faster-RCNN) for detecting both people and handguns. Body information is used in a post processing phase to assess the threat level or remove FPs, but it has no influence on the handgun detection step, so FNs cannot be solved.

Other works have used body pose through different approaches. Salido *et al.* [20] studied the impact of modifying the training datasets adding body pose overlays to the original images. Results showed that for some detectors the metrics improved. However, the pose information in this case is used in a pre-processing step to enrich the input images, but it still rely only on visual features when training. Velasco-Mata *et al.* [21] proposed a combined architecture that merges the output mask of a base handgun detector, YOLOv3, and a body pose detection heatmap. As a result, the model outputs grayscale images of potential handgun locations. However, the performance of this method depends highly on a manually established threshold for the grayscale images to find the best trade-off between FPs and FNs for each dataset. Ruiz-Santaquiteria *et al.* [22] also described a method which uses body pose information to help recognize handguns. This method is based on a 2D body pose estimator to extract both pose keypoints and hand region bounding boxes. Then, two independent CNNs are designed to process body pose images and hand region images respectively. Finally, the output of the two branches are combined to output a detection decision. This method is similar to our proposed approach but it only relies on CNN-based architectures for both visual and pose feature extraction.

Recently, the increasing interest on transformer-based architectures for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks has driven its application in computer vision problems such as image recognition or object detection. This architecture was originally presented in 2017 [23] and is based on multi-head self-attention layers. The main objective of these mechanisms, especially the transformer encoder branch, is to process a sequence of data to generate an enriched feature representation containing contextual information from all the components of the sequence. This feature representation can then be used to solve several NLP tasks. For image classification, Dosovitskiy *et al.* [24] proposed a method based on the previously described transformer architecture, the so-called Vision Transformer (ViT). In this case, no CNN is needed, the original image is divided into patches of fixed size (16x16) and then passed through a set of multi-head self-attention layers. After the transformer encoder, whose output contains an enriched feature representation of the entire sequence, a feed-forward network is included to generate the class probabilities. However, this method required a large amount of data and over two full days of computation for training. The Distilled data-efficient Image Transformer (DeiT), introduced by Touvron *et al.* [25], is a modified version of ViT, which is trained using a teacher-student strategy to effectively learn from a CNN (the teacher) during both pre-training and fine-tuning. The loss function of DeiT architecture considers teacher predictions, so the transformer model (the student) is penalised when it misclassifies its own or the teacher's predictions. Thanks to the prior information that can be learned from the CNN, it needs much less data for training.

Fig. 1. Proposed architecture.

Here, we propose a new handgun detection architecture based on combining two different models, one trained to distinguish body poses and the other to classify hand image regions. Different backbone models have been tested, including transformer-based models. We also process body posture information differently than in previous work.

3. Proposed method

A visual representation of the proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 1. First, the input image is passed through a body pose detector to obtain a representation of the human body (2D coordinates for each joint) for each located person. This pose information is then used to generate hand region images (image patches around hand locations) and a keypoint matrix (normalized 2D coordinates and detection confidence). Two independent models are then used to extract both the visual features for each image patch and the body pose features. The two feature vectors are combined and passed through a feed-forward model to generate the prediction for each image patch. Finally, an optional CNN-based model is included to filter out false positives. Each step of the proposed method is explained in detail in the following subsections.

3.1. Body pose estimation

The objective of human body pose estimation is to identify and classify the joints in the human body (wrists, elbows, neck, etc.). In general, this information is extracted as a set of 2D or 3D coordinates, also known as keypoints, which together describe the pose of a person.

OpenPose is one of the most used architectures for 2D body pose estimation. It was proposed in 2019 by Cao *et al.* [26] and it is based on a VGG-19 for feature extraction. The architecture is composed of two branches, the first one is intended to predict a confidence map for each body part and the second predicts the degree of association between keypoints. In our work, the *OpenPose* method is applied for two different tasks. The first one is estimating the body keypoints of the individuals in the image, which will be used in further steps of the method. The output of the model is composed of a set of 25 keypoints and each one is defined by 3 values, the first two are the (x, y) 2D coordinates and the third value is the decision confidence. Fig. 2 shows an example body pose estimation performed with *OpenPose*.

Pose keypoints are also used as a type of region proposal technique. Instead of checking the whole image, only the hand locations will be taken into account. Image patches are calculated as

bounding boxes around the wrist keypoints. Each image patch is resized using the bilinear interpolation method to a fixed image size of 224x224. Then, each patch is passed through the visual feature extraction backbone. The same resize/interpolation procedure is applied in both training and inference time.

3.2. Pose processing model

Human body pose has been successfully used for action recognition [27]. 2D estimated skeletons can be representative enough to predict common activities such as running, playing basketball, cycling, etc. Body posture when carrying or shooting a handgun is also distinctive from other common activities, especially in places where video surveillance is used.

As part of the proposed architecture for this work, a body pose processing model has been developed to recognize body poses between two classes, dangerous poses (i.e. those of people carrying or shooting handguns) and non-dangerous poses, for any other pose. Other approaches have also used body pose classifiers to this end [22]. However, the body pose was processed as an image (like that of Fig. 2b without the keypoint numbers) that is fed to a standard CNN architecture. Although the results in that case seemed quite promising, the use of images for pose data processing has some disadvantages. The first one is the amount of useless information, as most of the image is composed of a black background and only the body skeleton is represented. On the other hand, typical CNN architectures contain a larger number of training parameters compared to simpler feed-forward networks, which can perform well for this task.

In this work, we propose a simpler way to process the body pose information. Instead of generating 2D images, the body pose is encoded as a numerical feature matrix containing the 2D keypoint coordinates. In *OpenPose*'s output, all coordinates are computed with respect to the image origin, so a pre-processing step is needed to normalize them. This normalisation fixes the coordinate origin on each detected person's neck keypoint j_0 , if detected. The remaining body keypoints k_n are calculated following Eq. 1:

$$k_n = (j_n - j_0) / |\vec{j_0 j_1}| \quad (1)$$

where j_n is the original 2D point for the n^{th} joint and $|\vec{j_0 j_1}|$ is the distance between the neck and the lumbar spine keypoint j_1 , taken as reference. With this normalization process, only the relative locations between keypoints are taken into account, thereby removing some irrelevant information such as the location of the person within the image, the camera distance or the image resolution. At least 12 keypoints (half of the total possible keypoints) need to be

Fig. 2. Body pose estimation with *OpenPose*[26]: (a) shows the pose skeleton overlaid on an example image; (b) shows the keypoint distribution over the human body.

Fig. 3. Pose processing architecture.

detected, including the neck keypoint, to consider a person as detected. If no people are detected in an image, no handgun detections are generated.

The architecture used for the body pose classifier is a small feed-forward network. The input is a 25x3 matrix, that is, each one of the *OpenPose* joints with the (x, y) normalized coordinates and a detection confidence value $C \in [0, 1]$. Non-detected keypoints are filled with zeros, including the confidence value. Then, the flattened matrix is passed through a fully-connected layer of 16 nodes with the ReLu activation function. After training, this layer will be used as the pose feature vector. Finally, only in the training step of this model, another fully-connected layer of a single node gives the classification output (“Dangerous pose” vs “Other pose”). This last layer is only used for training this model independently, and

is removed when training the combined method. Fig. 3 shows the pose processing network diagram.

3.3. Handgun detection architecture

Here, we propose combining the body pose classifier with a network that processes image patches. The handgun detection problem has been therefore cast as a hand region classification that leverages both the content inside the hand region and the pose information to perform the final decision. The last feature vectors obtained with the two independent branches are concatenated before the last fully-connected layer, which carries out the classification between the two classes: “Handgun” or “No handgun”.

Fig. 4. Comparison between IoU and IoMin metrics for 3 different overlaps.

The true labels for the image patches are calculated automatically using the overlap ratio between these patches and the ground truth bounding boxes (handgun labels). The Intersection over Minimum (IoMin) function is used:

$$IoMin(A, B) = \text{area}(A \cap B) / \min(\text{area}(A), \text{area}(B)) \quad (2)$$

where A and B are the two bounding boxes whose overlapping ratio is being calculated. The reason for using this metric instead of the Intersection over Union (IoU) is related to the size differences between the bounding boxes of the image patches and the ground truth labels. For this particular problem, the objective is to recognize whether a pistol is present in an image, not to determine its exact limits, so IoMin allows for a better overlap measurement. Fig. 4 shows a comparison between IoU and IoMin in different scenarios. Although this metric still considers the overlap between the two bounding boxes, it does not penalize the size difference. IoMin has been also applied in recent handgun detection methods to measure the overlap ratio [21,22]. This metric is also used to calculate the evaluation metrics (TPs, FPs, FNs) and to check if two image patches overlap. Only one image patch is considered if a person is holding a handgun with both hands.

Different backbones have been tested for visual feature extraction of image patches, based on both CNN or transformer architectures. The YOLOv3 feature extractor, Darknet-53 [12], has been selected due to the good performance achieved by YOLO detectors for handgun detection in previous works. This architecture is composed of 53 convolutional layers with 3x3 and 1x1 kernel sizes. Residual connections, introduced by the ResNet model, are included after each convolution block to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, helping in the activation signal propagation. Other CNNs, like ResNet-50 [28], EfficientNet-B4 [29] and ConvNeXt-Base [30], have also been tested for comparison purposes. ResNet-50 is a well known architecture that has been widely used as backbone for several object detection architectures (e.g., Faster-RCNN) due to its good performance-complexity ratio. EfficientNet introduced a scaling method in terms of network width, depth and image resolution that achieves better accuracy and efficiency than previous CNNs. Finally, ConvNeXt is a recent approach that introduces several improvements (related to the network design and training techniques) to a standard ResNet architecture to achieve top-1 ImageNet accuracy.

As explained in Section 2, transformers are beginning to be used for computer vision problems, such as image classification or object detection. However, as far as authors know, this is the first time that transformer architectures have been used for handgun detection. In this work, ViT and DeiT encoders [24,25], composed of 12 multi-head self-attention layers, are also used for the feature extraction of hand region images.

All of these feature extractor architectures have been previously trained on ImageNet with an image size of 224x224. Only Darknet-53 comes pre-trained with a different image size, 256x256. The training process of the proposed method is performed in two different steps. First, the pose processing model is separately trained to distinguish between “Dangerous poses” and “Other poses”. Af-

ter that, the feature vector of this pose processing model is concatenated with the visual feature vector (1x16 values for each one) and passed through a last fully-connected layer (block “Hand patch classification” in Fig. 1). All of these components are then optimized in a second training process, in which the objective is to classify each hand patch between “Handgun” and “No handgun” classes, using in this way both visual and pose features. Fig. 5 shows how both branches are combined.

3.4. False positive filtering

Another frequent problem in object detectors is an unacceptable number of FPs, which can lead to the deactivation of these detectors when applied in real-life surveillance systems. In our case this problem may appear with objects of everyday use, particularly with smartphones, which nowadays can be found very frequently in our hands. For this reason, our proposed method also includes an optional module to filter FPs in scenarios where there is an excessive number of FPs in the base model, as discussed in Section 5. This module is applied in a sequential fashion over the base model predictions (candidate decisions) to distinguish between correctly classified regions (TPs), and incorrectly classified regions (FPs), for the handgun class.

In essence, this FP filter is a Darknet-53 CNN trained on a set of TPs and FPs image patches predicted by the base model. As the number of FPs is much smaller than that of TPs, a class weight estimation has been applied, modifying the uniform class weights. In this way, mistakes in samples with a higher class weight are more penalized, giving more emphasis to that class. Setting the class weights according to the number of images of each class, the unbalanced dataset effect is mitigated. In addition to this, data augmentation techniques such as random rotations, horizontal flipping or zooming have also been applied. At inference time, image patches classified as handgun class by the base model are passed through this FP filtering model, performing a second classification to remove possible FPs.

4. Experiments

4.1. Dataset description

The proposed architecture is designed to be used in video surveillance scenarios, implemented in CCTV surveillance systems. Unfortunately, existing public handgun datasets contain handgun profile images with a homogeneous background (e.g., gun selling websites), which are quite different from the images obtained by CCTV cameras [11,31].

In this work, data was collected from different sources looking for a wide variety of contexts and image features, including publicly available datasets, YouTube video sequences and even synthetic data extracted from video games. The first data source included in this study is the *Guns Movies Database* [32]. It contains 7 laboratory-shot movies of people holding handguns indoor, from the point of view of a video surveillance camera. From these videos, 500 images of 640x480 pixels were extracted, which contains a total of 500 handguns. On the other hand, 12 *YouTube* video sequences were collected and processed, extracting 650 frames of 1920x1080 pixels which contains a total of 750 handguns. These videos show people in several outdoor shooting ranges, designed specifically for firearm usage qualifications, training or competitions. Recent video games can be another important source for handgun images. For this work, 540 synthetic images of size 3840x2160, which contains 540 handguns, from the popular video game *Watch Dogs 2* were collected from video sequences of different in-game locations and camera configurations. Finally, the

Fig. 5. Combined architecture.

well known COCO dataset [33] was also used to complete and balance the dataset with non-handgun images, specifically with images containing common hand-held objects such as smartphones. A total of 1825 images of variable resolution were collected from this dataset. Except for the COCO images, which do not need labels, the remaining collected images were manually labelled by the authors, saving the bounding box coordinates of each located handgun.

In general, CCTV images are typically characterized by large camera distances, low resolution and poor lightning conditions. However, as explained before, it is difficult to find public datasets of CCTV images containing handguns. Thus, to better simulate these specific conditions, different versions of the original collected dataset have been generated. Hereinafter, in this document the original dataset is named as *dataset A*. Also, two additional versions of *dataset A* are used in this work to test the performance of the proposed methods under more difficult conditions. First, to simulate environments with scarce or poor illumination, a darkened version of the dataset was generated modifying the *Value* component in the HSV color space for all images. This modified dataset is named as *dataset B*. Finally, as camera distance is another relevant factor in the detection performance (especially for small objects), another version of the original dataset was generated reducing the image size by a half and filling the rest of the image with black pixels to preserve the original image resolution. This modified dataset is named as *dataset C*. To illustrate the appearance of the source images used and the different dataset versions, some samples¹ are presented in Fig. 6. The dataset will be available from the corresponding author on request.

4.2. Dataset partition

For the development of the proposed architecture, the dataset introduced in the previous section is divided into different subsets. Each of them is used to train and evaluate first, the body pose classifier separately, and then the complete combined architecture, which includes the trained pose classifier.

First, for optimizing the body pose processing model separately, samples of images containing people carrying handguns

Table 1

Dataset partition for the body pose classifier training and for the complete combined model training.

Class	Train	Validation	Test	All
Handgun	3170 519	396 129	396 259	3962 907
No handgun	3496 259	437 64	437 129	4370 452
All	6666 778	833 193	833 388	8332 1359

(e.g., firearms practice at shooting ranges) and samples of people in everyday situations, preferably carrying common hand-held objects, are needed. For this, a balanced set of samples from *dataset A* (original images without any modification), are extracted. Also, data augmentation is applied to significantly increase the number of samples for each class. This procedure is explained in Subsection 4.3. As usual, this dataset is also partitioned in three subsets for training, validation and test.

To train the complete combined model another dataset partition is needed. In this case, we want to optimize the final layers of the model once the output features of the previously trained pose model have been concatenated to the output of the hand region classifier. Due to the fact that they are based on pre-trained models on a larger dataset (ImageNet [34] for the hand region classifier and the aforementioned dataset partition for the pose classifier branch) it is not necessary to have a large number of images for this step. These images are all obtained from a different subset of *dataset A*. Table 1 shows the number of images per class in each subset

Altered images in *dataset B* and *dataset C* are only used to test the proposed approaches in conditions similar to those of CCTV video surveillance environments, specifically simulating conditions of poor lightning and large camera distance. Finally, to train the FP filter, a set of TP and FP image patches predicted by the base model were also generated from a subset of *dataset A* composed of 515 patches (400 TPs and 115 FPs), all resized to 224x224. 80% of the patches were used for training, 10% for validation and the remaining 10% for testing.

4.3. Data augmentation

Using a sufficient amount of data during the training process of a machine learning model is essential to obtain an acceptable

¹ Images shown are cropped to fit into the figure. Actual image size may vary

Fig. 6. Sample images of the datasets used. Each row corresponds to the datasets: from up to down, *dataset A*, *dataset B* and *dataset C* respectively. Each column shows the different data sources: from left to right, *Guns Movies Database* [32], a *YouTube* sample, a synthetic image extracted from *Watch Dogs 2* video game and a no-handgun image from *COCO* dataset [33]. Best viewed in color.

performance, especially for deep learning-based models. Unfortunately, this sufficient amount of data is usually quite high, requiring a great deal of manual work to collect and annotate the data. The presence of large public and labeled datasets helps to solve this problem in many cases, but it is not always possible to find enough specific datasets to face a certain problem, such as the one presented in this work. However, widely used techniques such as transfer learning or data augmentation allow us to obtain very good results without the need for large amounts of data to optimize the models.

In our work we have two models, initially independent, which are combined to achieve more robust results because different information is considered. The first model is an image classifier, whose goal is to recognize handguns in cropped regions of the original image (areas around human hands). Training this classifier from scratch using recent CNN-based deep learning architectures would require a large number of images, as discussed above. In order to significantly reduce the number of images needed, transfer learning is used. In this work, we start from models which have been pre-trained with ImageNet [34] and a specific training (fine-tuning) is performed on the dataset collected for this work, introduced in the previous subsections. Data augmentation has also been applied. In addition to the color modification and image scaling carried out to generate *dataset B* and *dataset C*, for the training of the complete combined model, horizontal flipped images have been generated, thus doubling the number of training images.

On the other hand, in order to train the body pose classifier it is necessary to have a large number of pose examples of each class because the model must be trained from scratch. For this reason, a data augmentation method has been developed which makes it possible to generate a large number of pose samples starting from a base set of images. This method is based on a 3D pose detector [35]. First, the 3D pose of each individual located in each image

is obtained through the 3D pose detector. This step generates a set of 3D coordinates corresponding to each pose keypoint of the image, including estimated points for body limbs that cannot be seen. Then, using these 3D coordinates, a 3D scene is simulated, and 2D coordinates are obtained depending on the camera position, which can be changed freely. Fig. 7 shows random subject axis rotations and virtual camera movements. This procedure generates, from a single pose, different points of view, which are in fact new data that can be used to train the body pose processing network.

4.4. Results

To evaluate the performance of the proposed method several experiments have been carried out. The test partition of *dataset A*, *B* and *C* are used to obtain the performance metrics. None of these images have been utilized in the training or evaluation steps in any of the previously described models. Please refer to the supplementary material for more details about the training settings of all modules.

The metrics used for the performance assessment are the most commonly used for object detection: *Precision* or ratio of correctly detected objects over all positive predictions of a certain class, *Recall*, or ratio of correctly detected objects over all ground truth objects of a certain class, and *Average Precision* score (AP), which is the area under the *Precision-Recall* curve. This curve shows the trade-off between *Precision* and *Recall* for different detection thresholds. A high area under the curve represents both high *Recall* and high *Precision*. The proposed method outputs a classification decision for each image patch (hand region image). To evaluate it as a detector, the bounding boxes of the image patches predicted as handgun class are selected as the final output for the handgun detector.

Fig. 7. Random camera rotations in the simulated 3D pose view. The hand holding a handgun is marked in red for clarity: (a) original RGB image; (b)-(d) pose augmentations. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Evaluation metrics (%AP). All variants of the proposed architecture are highlighted in the table. ViT+Pose variant is recommended as the best (see Section 5).

Method	Dataset A	Dataset B	Dataset C
YOLOv3 [12]	85.32	77.75	72.92
Faster-RCNN [10]	89.31	84.19	80.90
Basit et al. [19]	60.68	56.52	46.67
Velasco-Mata et al. [21]	64.62	59.37	47.13
Salido et al. [20]	83.68	79.97	67.79
Ruiz-Santaquiteria et al. [22]	89.02	84.64	85.20
ResNet-50	86.79	68.98	80.44
ResNet-50+Pose	87.92	80.48	85.95
EfficientNet-B4	87.76	78.72	81.65
EfficientNet-B4+Pose	89.58	84.32	85.36
ConvNeXt-Base	89.52	78.96	87.27
ConvNeXt-Base+Pose	90.50	80.78	88.71
Darknet53	84.93	74.69	81.14
Darknet53+Pose	92.76	88.00	90.08
Darknet53+Pose+FP filter	91.84	86.82	90.08
DeiT	87.46	83.66	85.87
DeiT+Pose	89.10	82.69	87.20
ViT	89.80	82.95	87.14
ViT+Pose (proposed)	91.73	84.98	88.98

In addition to the metrics obtained by the proposed method, which includes several architectures for visual feature extraction, some recent state of the art handgun detectors which also apply body pose information have been included in the experiments for comparison purposes. Since Salido et al. [20] introduced several approaches, for this test we have selected “YOLOv3 with pose” method, which showed the highest F1 score in their paper. Moreover, highly optimized and widely used object detectors such as Faster-RCNN and YOLOv3, which do not rely on pose-based data, have also been tested. AP score percentages for all methods and datasets are summarized in Table 2. The IoMin function has been used to generate the TPs, FPs and FNs for all methods, calculating the overlap between the predicted bounding boxes and the ground truth data (using 0.5 as the overlap threshold). As shown in the table, the proposed method improves the results achieved by previous approaches on all datasets for most backbones tested.

Although AP is a good metric to summarize the performance of object detectors, Precision-Recall curves can provide us with valuable additional information. In Fig. 8 the Precision-Recall curves of some methods are plotted. Some approaches are omitted for clarity. Only the results for dataset A are shown, since the results on dataset B and C are similar.

5. Discussion

Results presented in Table 2 and Fig. 8 show that including additional information, such as the human body pose in this case, can help to improve handgun detection. Our results improve on other methods, including those that leverage body pose. Furthermore, an ablation study has also been performed, removing the pose processing branch to assess the contribution of this component in the classifier output. The table shows the results of both approaches for each feature extractor, with and without including the pose branch. In most cases, the pose branch allows to achieve a higher AP (up to 10% in some cases). This can be explained by the fact that in certain difficult cases (e.g., small handguns or partially occluded), visual features alone are not sufficient to detect the object, while the additional body pose features included allows the correct recognition in such cases.

“Darknet-53+Pose” approach obtains the highest AP score on all datasets. However, despite the good results achieved in terms of Recall, Precision decreases significantly when reaching the highest Recall values due to FPs (see Fig. 8). The “Darknet-53+Pose+FP filter” approach, which adds the proposed FP filtering step, removes a large number of FPs, achieving an improvement of 13% in the Precision score. On the other hand, the AP score is also slightly reduced (around 1%) due to some TPs incorrectly removed. For this reason, applying the FP filter to methods with a low FPs rate could lead to a reduction in the overall AP score without a significant improvement in the Precision score, and therefore in this work is only applied in the “Darknet-53+Pose” approach.

The transformer-based feature extractors show the best trade-off between overall AP score and FPs, especially the “ViT+Pose” approach, when the pose branch is added, with up to 91.73% in AP and up to 97% in Precision. As far as authors know, this is the first time that transformer-based approaches are used for handgun detection.

The main objective of conducting experiments with modified datasets dataset B and dataset C is to assess the performance of the proposed method on deteriorated images, i.e., modified images to simulate CCTV-like environments, such as poor lightning conditions or large camera distances. Even though the tested models were only trained with unmodified images (i.e. dataset A), the last two columns of the table shows that the proposed approaches achieve remarkable results with low performance degradation.

Fig. 9 illustrates the benefits of the proposed contributions. Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b show that using the same backbone model for visual feature extraction (ViT), including body pose features, allows for the correct detection of certain handguns where visual weapon features are insufficient. Fig. 9c and Fig. 9d show how the proposed

Fig. 8. Precision-Recall curves on dataset A. Axes are constrained between 0.75 and 1 for Precision and between 0.45 and 1 for Recall for better view. Best viewed in color.

Fig. 9. Detection examples. ViT (a) and ViT+Pose (b) show how the generated pose features allow detecting handguns when visual weapon features are not enough. CNN+Pose (c) and CNN+Pose+FP filter (d), being the CNN the Darknet53, show how the FP filter helps to reduce the number of FPs.

FP filtering model helps to remove incorrectly classified regions by the base model.

6. Conclusions

In this work we propose a novel method for the detection of handguns in CCTV video surveillance images. A human body pose estimator, *OpenPose*, has been used to predict the 2D body joint coordinates. These keypoints are applied for two main purposes, extracting image patches from hand regions and generating normalized keypoint matrices. Then, two independent models generate visual and pose features, which are combined and passed through some feed-forward layers to generate image patch predictions. The experiments performed show that for the tested datasets the proposed approach improves other methods in terms of AP, including some recent ones which also include additional pose information. The combined visual and pose features allow the correct recognition of image patches in certain environments where the standard visual features are not sufficient. To analyze the contribution of the body pose processing branch over the full architecture, the tests have been performed using different architectures for visual feature extraction with and without adding the body pose features, reaching higher AP scores with the pose-included approaches in almost all cases.

Regarding the main limitations of the proposed method and future lines of work in this field, it is important to point out that the performance depends to a large extent on the pose estimation method. If certain keypoints are not identified or incorrectly

detected, later steps of the method could fail. While much of the method can be executed in parallel, adding models like the body pose estimator or FP filtering model increases inference time. An in-depth analysis of performance in terms of execution time should be performed to validate its use in real time devices. Finally, different approaches for handgun detection and FPs reduction may be explored. In this work, only individual images are used and temporal information is not considered. Using video sequences in combination with the recent transformer-based architectures could help in detecting dangerous objects and also filtering FPs.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary material

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